

AMIRÉS

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN HEALTHCARE AND LIFE SCIENCES EVENT

REPORT

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly becoming part of our lives, with the potential of facilitating and accelerating processes. Life sciences and healthcare are not the exception. Alone in the US, based on a survey from McKinsey in 2025, 85% of respondents (incl. healthcare payers, health systems, and healthcare services and technology groups) were exploring or had already adopted generative AI tools¹.

At the same time, in life sciences AI tools have increased since the Nobel Prize in Chemistry awarded in 2024 to scientists² who developed the generative AI system AlphaFold, which predicts protein structures, revolutionizing the field of proteomics, molecular biology, drug discovery and biomedical research. A 2025 survey showed that 96% of life sciences leaders believe AI tools will be essential within two years³.

The following report captures European-based advances of AI in different branches of life sciences and healthcare presented at the “AI in healthcare and life sciences” workshop held in Prague, Czechia on June 10, 2025 organized by [AMIRES](#) in the frame of [NAP4DIVE project](#). These included from AI applications in the military, radiology, drug discovery, cell tracking to legal implications in AI. The workshop was structured around an opening keynote speech, followed by 3 dedicated sessions:

- 1) AI in Life sciences*
- 2) AI-enabled care*
- 3) Enabling AI applications*

¹ [Generative AI in healthcare: Current trends and future outlook | McKinsey](#)

² Demis Hassabis and John Jumper of Google DeepMind , and David Baker of the University of Washington. [NobelPrize.org](#)

³ [AI agents are transforming the healthcare and life sciences industry | ZDNET](#)

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	4
2. Report from the “AI in Healthcare and Life sciences”workshop	4
2.1. Introduction to the AI in Healthcare and Life sciences event	4
2.2. Keynote presentation: AI applications in the military.....	5
2.3. AI in Life sciences session	6
2.4. AI-enabled care.....	9
2.5. Enabling AI applications.....	14
2.6. Summary /conclusions/take aways.....	18
3. Annex 1: Agenda	19

1. Introduction

Even AI applications might seem recent, the history of the AI starts in the middle of 1950, with the coined term of *Artificial Intelligence* in the Dartmouth Conference. Following by early AI systems used for chemical analysis and bacterial infections diagnosis in the 60s and 70s (DENDRAL and MYCIN⁴). However, its application remained limited in the clinical practice, and it was integrated only in the first decade of the 21st century as support of the diagnostics and imaging (e.g. radiology). In addition, AI was supporting electronic health records, robotics surgery and drug discovery. In the last five years AI solutions are used in clinical trial optimization, drug development, protein structure prediction, and others.

The importance of these tools is not ignored by funders, including the biggest public funding programme in Europe, Horizon Europe, which since it started in January 2021, 297 AI-related projects have been funded, for €57.7 million. In comparison to its predecessor programme, Horizon 2020, which funded 489 AI-related projects in all of the prior seven years of its duration. In addition, the Digital Europe Programme⁵ has dedicated over EUR 1 billion in 2021-2024 to support the deployment of AI. The AI Innovation Package and other initiatives are expected to mobilize up to €20 billion annually in public and private investments across Europe supporting startups and SMEs⁶. The EU is clearly positioning AI as a key enabler of innovation in healthcare and life sciences. This momentum is reflected in the growing number of funded initiatives tackling challenges from cancer diagnostics to clinical trial optimization.

The recent event, “*AI in Healthcare and Life Sciences*”, organized by AMIRES on the frame of NAP4DIVE EU-funded project at the Hotel Vienna House Diplomat on June 10, 2025, brought together experts and stakeholders to explore how these investments are translating into real-world impact — from predictive models and digital twins to ethical frameworks, non-animal testing strategies and clinical applications of AI. The convergence of policy, funding, and cutting-edge research marks a pivotal moment for AI-driven transformation in European health innovation. Importantly, this event highlighted the ethical and translational challenges that projects like NAP4DIVE are addressing — including the integration of non-animal models, BBB on chip technologies, and AI-powered decision-making in biomedical research.

2. Report from the “AI in Healthcare and Life sciences” workshop

2.1. Introduction to the AI in Healthcare and Life sciences event

[Cecilia Sahlgren](#) (Professor, Åbo Akademi University & Eindhoven University of Technology) and [Martina Nešverová](#) (Programme Manager, Health & Biotechnology, AMIRES) welcomed all participants to the event. With interesting numbers already mentioned above motivated the audience to hear more, which included more than 50 AI experts or aficionados.

Big amount of data is being generated continuously in life sciences, limiting further analysis. A single person is not able to process this amount of data, making scientists seek for automatic tools that will accelerate and support this need. Currently, molecular signalling- prove and test model for prediction, computer-based models are used at many levels of research for addressing this challenge. Other initiatives that exist are virtual cells, to monitor and analyse cells, having applications in research, healthcare and telemedicine.

⁴ [When Was AI First Used in Healthcare? The History of AI in Healthcare](#)

⁵ [European research development and deployment of AI | Shaping Europe’s digital future](#)

⁶ [Commission launches AI innovation package](#)

These tools are facilitators, however come with further requirements or challenges, such as trustworthiness, safety and high quality of data.

2.2. Keynote presentation: AI applications in the military

[Martin Majovsky](#) (Neurosurgeon, Associate Professor, Military University Hospital Prague) focused his talk on the adoption of new technologies in military medicine, including AI related.

AI is being applied in clinical practice decreasing paperwork, imaging analysis and many other applications. However still the question persists, how to implement AI in healthcare, how to implement it in remote hospitals, in places with limited resources, and in military healthcare. Prof. Majovsky addressed these questions.

Language is believed to be very human, however the machines through AI has proven is not completely true, and machines can learn language. LLMs (large language models) are computer language models based on a neural network with many parameters (typically billions of weights or more), trained on a very large amount of text, producing natural language. Tomas Mikolov, the most cited Czech scientist, classifies each word in different dimensions (mathematical space), providing a mathematical operation to words, developing the system Word2vec, an important element of the LLMs. The LLMs work through tokenisation, which divides text into tokens, and converting to words, providing predictions based on probability.

A commonly used term in AI is "hallucination," which originally refers to a pathological condition in humans. However, in the context of AI, it does not imply a malfunction or mental disorder. Instead, it describes instances where the model generates information that appears plausible but is factually incorrect or fabricated. These outputs often arise because the model is drawing from patterns in its training data, rather than accessing real-time or verified sources.

Multimodal models, which are widely used today, can access the internet, including databases such as PubMed in real time. Other models in use are the reasoning models, and agents, which execute an action if prompting. Prof. Majovsky presented AI-based applications used in the military practice such as a ventilator that uses LLM in a prehospital care setting for wounded soldiers. Three settings were tested among 42 participants doing it independently (without AI), with AI assistance, and AI independent. The results showed that the ventilator setting using AI independent performed better than the others.

Automatic X ray evaluation uses convolutional neuronal network, and is the most commonly used in clinical practice (chest and bone x-rays). A pilot usability study for automatic chest X-ray interpretation in field hospital conditions was performed, in which radiologists are not available. Using 159 anonymized chest Xray images, it was found higher diagnostic accuracy when participants used AI.

There is already use of LLM in routine tasks in medicine such as data extraction of EHRs (electronic health records), care reporting for insurers, etc. Further improvement into personalized LLMs, support on the decision for diagnosis and treatment, use of avatars and image analysis. Others are in surgical videos to predict the surgical step supported using robots. Further opportunities of AI to increase work efficiency, more accurate and faster diagnosis and treatments, standardization of care, potential of fewer healthcare workers, improved access, personalized medicine (risks list, dosage of medicines/drugs). However, with these also come some threats, such as data security, patient trust, system failures, cyberattacks, black box problem, loss of skills/medical judgement, legal liability.

Some of the questions raised were related to the potential of malfunctions on the system and the potential of losing skills on the medical doctors, as well as the adoption of avatars use that were also presented. In addition,

questions related to the consent from patients and the disagreement that the number of clinicians will be reduced, since the amount of work is increasing and the exams are more complex every year.

The following were the topics discussed after the attendees raised their questions:

- Confidentiality in AI-driven patient interactions: Ensuring trust while improving access to healthcare specialists
- Addressing the growing demand for healthcare specialists: Challenges and digital solutions
- Legal and ethical considerations in surgical data recording: Patient consent, data ownership, and regulatory oversight

2.3. AI in Life sciences session

This session presented the experts at the forefront of AI in life sciences: [Cecilia Sahlgren](#) Professor in Cell Biology at Åbo Akademi, [Vassilis Sarantos](#) , Director & CEO at RayFos Ltd, [Noemi Corcos](#), Translational Project Manager at Institute Gustave Roussy and [Carine Poussin](#), Head of AI in Life Sciences at CSEM,. The session was moderated by [Mariana Pacheco Blanco](#) (Programme Manager, AMIRES)

2.3.1. NAP4DIVE: Utilizing AI as non-animal tools to assess nanoparticle-mediated drug delivery over the BBB

Cecilia Sahlgren (Professor, Åbo Akademi University & Eindhoven University of Technology) presented the project recently started in January 2025, [NAP4DIVE](#).

Research for testing nanoparticles (NPs) as treatment for brain diseases costs 800 billion EUR per year. In addition, there is a poor understanding of the nanoparticles crossing the blood-brain barrier (BBB). The current gold standard is still the use of animals in preclinical models. However, in addition to harming animals, this is not a good representation of human biology; and alternative models are needed to address these shortcomings. Therefore, the NAP4DIVE project is developing a digital “nanoparticle design simulator” tool based on AI, and an organ on-chip-model to study BBB crossing. The NP design library will be based on the design-function relationships between the nanoparticles analysed and the BBB. At the end, the goal is to find five well performing nanoparticles to be tested in an industrial validation setting by Astra Zeneca

Scores of the nanoparticle (NP) will be established based on how it can penetrate the BBB and based on the NP physicochemical properties, this will guide further relevant design choices, reduce computer time and costs, and transparent model behaviour, making decisions. One challenge that exists in the BBB research is that is hard to distinguish if a nanoparticle crosses the BBB because of the permeability of the brain due to a disease or due to the intrinsic characteristics of the nanoparticle to go through the barrier.

Other examples of relevant AI tools used in life sciences are [EVONANO](#), which is a platform that treat virtual tumours with nanoparticles in complex tumour environments. In addition, [Physicell](#) is a virtual lab for multicellular complex systems, the virtual cell.

2.3.2. Real-Time Cell Tracking in Tumor-LN-oC Deploying ML models at the edge

Vassilis Sarantos (Director & CEO, RayFos Ltd.) presented the work done by UK-based SME Rayfos on the project [Tumor LN-OC](#), in which they are deploying a (quasi) real time cell segmentation and tracking using advanced machine learning (ML) techniques. Four main challenges have been identified in the deployment of these models:

- handling wide field of view images for ML processing, boundaries, specialized models to address these challenges (time),
- training data acquisition limitations – labelling and stained images – custom label free ML model having encouraging results achieved with brightfield and phase contrast imaging,
- deployment challenge-before the postprocess and quantifications such as cross-environment incompatibility, which they are solving using specific software’s to overcome this, cloud inference, edge inference (low compute and memory)
- General Tumor-LN-OC deployment challenges – requirement of the use of other applications (Tensor Flow graphs)

Within the model an input image sequence provides the cell tracking as output in form of videos and plots, showing directional movement of the cells. The semi supervised model, mostly trained on brightfield images, has promising results. This model has the possibility to be adjusted and trained for specific biological questions. The fine tuning can help support and eventually compliment the work of cell biologists in various research applications.

2.3.3. OASIS: Bridging Data and Decision-Making in ADC Treatment with AI

Noémie Corcos (Translational Project Manager, Institute Gustave Roussy) presented the project [OASIS](#).

Antibody-drug conjugates (ADCs) are transforming the therapeutic landscape of oncology by combining targeted antibody specificity with the cytotoxic potency of chemotherapeutic agents. More than 370 ADCs are under clinical development and 17 of them approved in different countries and their outstanding efficacy might lead them to ultimately replace standard chemotherapy . Despite their clinical success, major challenges remain, including heterogeneous responses across patients, limited predictive biomarkers, and insufficient tools to monitor treatment and detect resistance..

The European program OASIS (*Optimal methods to characterize ADC resistance in Solid tumors and Identify clinically useful biomarkers*) has been launched to develop and validate biomarkers that will improve patient stratification, guide clinical decision-making, and accelerate the implementation of ADCs in routine care.

The overarching goal of OASIS is to integrate liquid biopsy biomarkers with tissue- and imaging-based approaches to deliver clinically actionable tools for ADC therapies. Specifically, the program aims to:

- Identify predictive biomarkers of treatment benefit,
- Enable real-time monitoring of therapeutic response,
- Detect early mechanisms of resistance.

To achieve this goal, a large clinical trial, coordinated by Unicancer, will provide longitudinal blood and tissue samples from patients receiving ADCs, enhanced by a set of high-precision analyses:

- AI digital pathology and imaging of tumor tissues.
- Liquid biopsies and analysis of circulating tumor cells (CTCs).
- Tumor-derived organoids that mimic the real tumor microenvironment.

- High-throughput proteomics using Proximity Extension Assay (PEA) technology.
- Genomics and transcriptomics to map molecular alterations.
- ImmunoPET to visualize therapeutic targets in vivo.

All of these data will be integrated into a machine learning–based predictive model: the OASIS score, a decision-support tool for clinicians, based on ADC efficacy and toxicity.

To generate this model, data gathered from a large clinical trial, including a prospective and a retrospective cohort, will serve as the OASIS training set. The validation set will combine data from several closed clinical trials using different ADCs, as well as a new clinical trial, testing a new ADC.

Within this work, they will study the mechanisms that produce resistance, that can be related to the antibody, the payload or even other important aspects of the mechanisms of action of ADCs, like their ability to target effectively the cancer cells.

They will also establish optimal preclinical tools by the generation of a patient-derived organoids (PDO) biobank, capturing the various mechanisms of resistance that can occur under ADC treatment.

The AI digital pathology collection of tumour samples will include analysis of various cancer biomarkers, such as HER2, TROP2, Nectin-4, and their spatial distribution, as well as the tumour microenvironment, which could be used for the prediction. They will use then a multimodal model for prediction, using the knowledge based combining biomarkers in multivariate models and data based with deep learning model for multimodal integration, which will provide the optimal combination (i.e. OASIS prediction score).

OASIS will also develop a web application to be used by clinicians that will generate a report based on the OASIS prediction score with the ADC treatments available for the specific patients after inputting the data from the patient.

2.3.4. Personalized Medicine through AI: Integrating Multi-modal Data for Revolutionizing Healthcare

Carine Poussin (Head of AI for Life Sciences, CSEM) presented the projects in which CSEM is involved using AI and towards personalized medicine.

CSEM is a Swiss applied research and technology innovation center whose mission is to support industry and academic partners in accelerating the development of their technology/product and tech transfer it for real-world application(s), industrialization and commercialization. Through CSEM tools for life sciences, they integrate research and development in biosensing, cell technologies, lab automation and AI for life sciences.

CSEM tailors predictive AI solutions by integrating and contextualizing multi-modal data to accelerate innovation in Life Sciences (diagnostics, therapeutics, longevity, personalization and prevention). They develop customized predictive AI solutions, such as multimodal data integration, AI engine, predictive AI (drug response, disease risk, disease severity, biological age, etc) through tools such as digital twins. They develop new architectures for neuronal networks that can provide predictions and other insights to “avoid” the black box issue.

Carine Poussin provided an example/ use case of a multimodal data-based patient stratification platform for multiple myeloma for clinical decision support. This system uses similarity metric, a similarity network through data fusion, which is represented graphically and classified the patients based on the predictions to drug responses (positive response, no response, adverse response). The multiple myeloma cohort was 138 patient

samples and 32 clinical features, pharmacoscopy for 61 drugs. (multiplex labelling of immune cells-5663 plasma cell proteins and 64 cytokines, morphology)⁷.

AI-driven solutions advantages in healthcare:

1. Deep insights into patient clusters
2. Predictive modelling capabilities
3. High adaptability

2.3.5. Topics of discussion during Q&A session

The following topics were raised for discussion during Q&A of “AI in life sciences” session:”

- **Data Readiness & Research Enablement**
 - Challenges in obtaining, delivering, and preparing data for research: Addressing fragmentation, standardization, and access barriers.
 - Evaluating data input quality: The role of medical specialists in assessing data relevance and tool performance.
 - Accessibility and openness of developed tools: Exploring open access models and licensing types.
- **Deployment & Real-World Integration**
 - Deploying AI tools in preventive care: Opportunities and challenges in collaboration with health insurance providers.
 - Model specifications and scientific support: How AI models are tailored to assist researchers and clinicians effectively.

2.4. AI-enabled care

This session gathered leaders who are shaping the future of AI in healthcare: [Dr. Erik Ranschaert](#), Diagnostic Radiologist at St. Nikolaus Hospital, Eupen, Senior Medical Advisor, and Visiting Professor at Ghent University, [Terence J. Quinn](#), Professor and Physician of cardiovascular and metabolic health at the University of Glasgow, [Cristian Izquierdo Morcillo](#), Scientific Lead at the University of Barcelona, and [Max Heiland](#), Medical Director at the Clinic for Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin. This session was moderated by [Panagiotis Chatzis](#) (Project Manager, AMIRES)

[Zdenek Havel](#), from [CzechInvest](#) (a state contributory organization subordinate to the Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic) briefly introduced the opportunities they offer to fund companies for technologies, especially AI.

2.4.1. The present and future of AI in Radiology

Erik Ranschaert (Diagnostic Radiologist, Senior Medical Advisor, Visiting Professor at Ghent University) gave a talk to provide an overview of the use of AI in radiology, a medical specialty in which AI technologies are used the most and one of the most advanced application areas of AI in healthcare.

In the last 3 years, commercial AI products increased more than 100%. Based on the Health AI register 244 CE marked AI applications exist. AI technologies in radiology plays a crucial role in identifying patterns and categorizing findings, improving the diagnosis. Most of the AI solutions currently used in radiology are in neurology (CTs and MRI), chest (pulmonary), musculoskeletal, and mammography.

⁷ [Pistilli et al, ESMO 2024; Mosele et al, Nature Medicine 2023](#)

Fracture detection in emergency rooms using AI can also help detect some fractures that the human eye is not detecting, due to tiredness for example. They are more efficient in diagnosing and facilitating the decision making, which improves the overall care quality.

Another area positively impacted with the use of AI is for the pulmonary embolism detection, especially in complex cases, which are life-threatening and require immediate action. They support the work of radiologists in the emergency radiology practice.

In a recent doctoral thesis⁸, investigators studies use of AI on MRI images for detecting brain metastasis. The AI application reduced the reading time, and led to more accurate results. After this study, they identified the advantages of AI use for this application

- Diagnostic precision
- Enhanced efficiency
- Improved patient outcomes

Another example given was the **MASAI trial**- AI for mammography –, whose objective is to evaluate whether AI is as safe as traditional reading of mammography. For that purpose, images from 80 000 women aged 40-80 years were used, resulting in 20% more cancer detected, while decreasing the workload by up to 44%.

Despite significant advances in AI tools, still 70-80% of AI activities are considered to be in pilot and research phase, only 20-30% are already in clinical use in the EU. In the Netherlands, through the 6th edition of “AI monitor in hospitals”, it was found that from 43 hospitals in the study, 57% utilize AI in some capacity. This report also analysed to which degree hospitals are ready for AI, e.g. considering operating policies, technical infrastructure etc. One of the main motivations for hospital to adopt AI is that the use of AI promises to decrease workload of health care professionals.

Despite the immense potential, growth/uptake of AI solutions in the clinical practice is slow because of several reasons:

- Medical considerations, such as legal ethical doubts, lack of clinical awareness and the scientific validation
- Technical aspects, for example IT challenges, underfunded IT, shift to cloud infrastructures (plans for 1 year ahead)
- Organisational reasons, such as slow procurement (which takes 1 year), lack of AI champions, conservative medical culture
- Financial obstacles, for example no reimbursement, budget cuts and inflation, COVID19 effects

Generative AI (creating new content from learned patterns) enters in the evolution of AI uptake, which can be used for automated reporting, transcription, document summaries in hospitals. However, only 25% of hospitals studies have a long-term vision of AI strategy, and only 30% possess a formal AI policy.

One application of GenAI is the generation of synthetic images (MRI, CT), for example to avoid the use of contrast in bone assessment, to improve image quality, as a workflow support and predictive modelling. Some examples are to predict tumor evolution- AI providing more quantifiable information (more objective)- to detect if tumour is growing or reducing size. Another example is in the EU funded project [NetZeroAICT](#), which uses digital contrast to avoid the use of contrast agents in CT scans. AI-powered report generation ([a2radiology.ai](#)), which indicates possibilities of the AI can see, and radiologist have possibility to select the type of condition, and the report is written by the AI.

⁸ [Topff L, et al. Ranschaert ER, Groot Lipman KBW, Beets-Tan RGH. A Data-Centric Approach to Deep Learning for Brain Metastasis Analysis at MRI. Radiology. 2025 Jun;315\(3\):e242416.](#)

AI has matured in specific domains however challenges remain. AI ecosystem needs to mature for leashing all opportunities that AI brings. The future of AI in medicine is shaped on the following:

- GenAI will enable personalized medicine
- Earlier disease recognition improving preventing care
- Clinical acceptance required well define ethical and transparency frameworks
- The responsible AI need multistakeholder collaboration.

In the long term, AI will be replacing people, specially radiologists but mainly the ones who do not use AI. Therefore, Erik emphasised that radiologists who embrace AI will shape the future of the profession.

2.4.2. AI to assist stroke care and life after stroke - learnings from RES-Q+

Terry Quinn (Professor, University of Glasgow) spoke about the AI tools used in stroke care and on stroke survivors in the EU project [RES-Q+](#).

Dr. Quinn started his presentation with an analogy of the movie Terminator, and how AI can be considered to be “harder, better, faster and stronger” such as the Terminator, the role of the actor Arnold Schwarzenegger. Clinicians instead of being afraid of their use should embrace AI to make us “harder, better faster and stronger”.

Stroke care is exemplar of uncoordinated data, inefficient communication, poor support post discharge, long term follow up, which can be considered as well for other diseases. RES-Q+ is a Horizon Europe project that started in 2022, and is based on the RES-Q platform that uses a discharge importer, and a virtual assistant (VA).

Clinician VA (help clinicians to analyse treatment data to identify trends and areas of improvement) and patient VA (collect PROMs-patient-reported outcomes measurements and support survivors of stroke in their transition home), an AI enabled virtuous circle: based on the data from the patient asking VA specific questions to get information and alerting clinician when needed to adjust treatments/actions. The benefits for clinicians are: better overview of condition, possibility of remote follow up, compare with others; while for patients the main advantages include patient-clinician connection, self-management, and continuous monitoring. In the project, researchers track recovery assessment by weekly PROMs (stroke outcome and impact...), and conducting interviews with stroke survivors through workshops in the Czech Republic to get feedback from users. In the development of the VA, a process of choosing the best PROM is implemented, using the Rankin scale (stroke outcome) and the Nottingham ADL scale.

The RESQ+ project is planning for the next phase to run a large clinical study to test usability and adherence to the VA over 3 months, to develop the question-answering functionality using LLMs with clinician validated sources, and link the VA with hospital data to provide personalised answers based on predictive models. In addition, data is collected from stroke survivors (from charities in the UK, such as stroke association) precisely to know what it is important for them regarding stroke care.

2.4.3. Trustworthy AI in cardiology: AI4HF and DT4H insights

Cristian Izquierdo Morcillo (Scientific Lead at University of Barcelona) presented two EU funded projects that use AI for cardiology applications.

Trustworthy AI refers to AI systems that are designed, developed and deployed to operate reliably, ethically and transparently, prioritizing values such as safety and privacy. The 11 running projects at the University of Barcelona are built around the FUTURE AI guidelines, which come from Fairness, Universality, Traceability, Usability, Robustness and Explainability. The projects in detail presented were [DataTools4Heart](#) and [AI4HF](#). In the first one in which they develop a platform that enables the sharing and reuse of cardiology data across

Europe. For that, they are developing data harmonization tool (HL7 FHIR), NLP suite, federated learning for AI ML models, synthetic data generator tool, and virtual assistants- platform that enables sharing data in cardiology. Federated learning: central orchestrator but trained locally, in which the data doesn't leave the premises. The work in the project provides for patient care a universal, robust and unbiased model, which is scalable, and accessible. It adapts regarding the conditions of the location (such as with data from African countries), provides harmonized data, and is user friendly due to an assisted AI agent. It ensures security, privacy, it is validated in 3 use cases, designed to be traceable, and planned an external validation through open calls.

In addition, AI4HF project develops an AI solution for personalized risk assessment in chronic heart failure. To achieve that, they are developing similar tools, but also an AI passport, a continuous learning evaluation tool and an AI monitoring platform. The main characteristics of the project are the international collaboration of AI4HF, outside EU with the federated platform, and the patient involvement as main stakeholders, providing their feedback via surveys. This project uses a model repository and offers information about models for reproducibility, alarm system for model updates and data drift detection, dedicated explainability interface (difference between patients and AI researchers)

2.4.4. AI in Dental Care

Max Heiland (Director and Chairman Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery at Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin) provided insights on the use of AI on dental care as finding risks on several common diseases.

A clinical gap exists because a lot of data is taken at dentist's office, but this information is not generally shared with General Practitioners. It is possible that AI can provide more information from an Xray, however this should be proven through randomized controlled trials, which can optimize the workflow.

AI has a huge opportunity within the patient journey in the oral and maxillofacial surgery department, with several steps such as the screening, imaging, treatment planning, assessment and monitoring. For instance, AI has the potential to detect pathologies on panoramic views/dental radiographs in a study that started in 2016 (DENTISTAI⁹) in periapical lesions. Using 2900 anonymized images, annotated by 4 physicians, tested with 102 images by 24 dentists, this study showed that the AI had a precision of 0.69 and sensitivity of 0.51, and algorithm performance of F1 score of 0.58.

Use of AI in dentistry research has increased in the last years, automatic results based on different algorithms. The application of AI fall into the diagnostic, 3D reconstruction, monitoring, screening, and virtual planning. The automated detection of mandibular fractures using AI on more than 6000 panoramic radiographs¹⁰. The algorithm was trained on 1640 panoramic radiographs with and without fractures, having lowest classification accuracy (3/6 correctly classified) and highest classification performance (0.947).

In the case of detection carotid plaques (present in 3-15% of these radiographs), 7% show stenosis/calcifications of which 50% lead to an increased risk of stroke. Dentists are not trained to detect those, but an algorithm can support in identifying it and aid in early detection and prevention. A total of 6404 DICOM images were included for training and 37 for testing, confirming that the algorithm can assist in the detection of carotid plaques with a F1 score of 0.88¹¹.

⁹ [Endres MG, et al, Heiland M, Gaudin RA. Development of a Deep Learning Algorithm for Periapical Disease Detection in Dental Radiographs. Diagnostics \(Basel\). 2020 Jun 24;10\(6\):430.](#)

¹⁰ [Vinayahalingam, S., Max Heiland, Tabea Flügge & Robert Gaudin. et al. Detection of mandibular fractures on panoramic radiographs using deep learning. Sci Rep 12, 19596 \(2022\).](#)

¹¹ [Vinayahalingam S, van Nistelrooij N, Xi T, Heiland M, Bressemer K, Rendenbach C, Flügge T, Gaudin R. Detection of carotid plaques on panoramic radiographs using deep learning. J Dent. 2024 Dec;151:105432.](#)

Another pathology that can benefit from the use of AI on panoramic views is osteoporosis. This pathology is usually diagnosed through a dual energy Xray absorptiometry scan, the gold standard (that is usually done when the first fracture appears). In a recent study presented, it was demonstrated that a deep learning algorithm can early detect osteoporosis on dental radiographs, using 250 radiographs with a F1 score of 0.9714¹².

AI was also tested with regards to detection of oral cancer risk¹³. The oral squamous cell carcinomas have low sensitivity and specificity using visual diagnostics. 1406 clinical images were annotated, and the algorithm was trained on 1265 of these images, and tested on a separate set of 141 images, showing that the model used is a reliable method for detecting this type of cancer in clinical images, however further training with monogenous image datasets is necessary.

Segment 3D data is needed for reconstruction of fractures, tumours, resections, all of them that benefit of AI for more efficient surgical and treatment planning, and reduce the radiation exposure.

2.4.5. Topics of discussion during Q&A session

The following topics were raised for discussion during Q&A of “AI-enabled care” session:”

- **Legal, Ethical & Governance Aspects of AI in Healthcare**
 - Federated learning and legal hurdles: Challenges in obtaining legal sign-off and IT integration for federated learning architectures.
 - Data governance in surgical recordings: Patient consent, data ownership, and regulatory frameworks.
 - Ensuring fairness, transparency, and reliability in AI systems.
 - Addressing inequalities in digital health: Including risks of overlooking older patients or underserved populations.
- **Technical Integration & Infrastructure**
 - Hospital IT requirements for AI deployment: Adapting new systems to existing platforms and ensuring smooth integration.
 - Overcoming fragmented AI tools: Toward unified platforms for testing and deploying multiple applications.
 - Engaging IT departments early: Importance of cross-functional collaboration for successful implementation.
- **Data Quality, Access & Model Development**
 - Training models with diverse, high-quality data: Avoiding bias through multi-center datasets.
 - Accessibility of dental data for AI development.
 - Use of AI-generated synthetic images: Enhancing algorithm training with synthetic data.
- **Clinical Implementation & Validation**
 - Timing and complexity of clinical AI adoption: How hospital size and structure affect rollout.
 - Methodologies for clinical validation of AI tools.
 - Risk of foundation models outpacing narrow AI solutions: Strategic considerations for long-term adoption.
- **Human-Centered Design & Patient Engagement**
 - Working with end users to reduce inequalities: Adapting tools to real-world clinical scenarios.
 - Integration of virtual assistants into clinical workflows.

¹² [Gaudin, R., et al., Heiland, M., & von See, C. \(2024\). Enhanced Osteoporosis Detection Using Artificial Intelligence: A Deep Learning Approach to Panoramic Radiographs with an Emphasis on the Mental Foramen. Medical Sciences, 12\(3\), 49](#)

¹³ [Flügge, T., Gaudin, R., Sabatakakis, A. et al. Detection of oral squamous cell carcinoma in clinical photographs using a vision transformer. Sci Rep 13, 2296 \(2023\).](#)

- Improving recovery tracking with Patient-Reported Outcome Measures (PROMs): Especially for stroke survivors.

2.5. Enabling AI applications

This session brought distinguished speakers on topics that are required for a trustworthy, fair and sustainable AI solution: [Michal Koščík](#), Head of the Institute of Public Health at the Faculty of Medicine, Masaryk University, Czechia, [Petra Zarska](#), an Intellectual Property manager and analyst at AMIRES, [Sepinoud Azimi](#), Assistant Professor at TU Delft and [John Kellas](#) is a researcher at the Nuffield Department of Surgical Sciences, Oxford University, and an Innovation and Community Engagement Consultant at Bristol Health Partners. It was moderated by [Kristin Lipus](#) (Senior Project Manager, AMIRES)

2.5.1. Legal Implications of the European Health Data Space for Research

Michal Koščík (Head of Department of Public Health & Vice Dean, Masaryk University Brno) spoke about the European Health Data Space for Research (EHDS) and the legal implications for researchers.

The EHDS promises that individuals will take control of their health data and facilitate the exchange to fit for the delivery of healthcare across the EU, being the primary use of data. Having as a secondary use of data, a consistent, trustworthy, and efficient system for reusing health data for research, innovation, policy-making, and regulatory activities.

Naturally, the main objective of gathering patient-specific data is to be used to directly support care of these patients. However the wider vision for researchers is to:

1. Share access to high quality data
2. Ensure standardization and interoperability
3. Use data for accelerated innovation
4. Support ethical and responsible AI
5. Enable collaboration across borders

EHDS is based on the existing framework of the GDPR, the data governance act, data act and the network and information systems directive. The intention is that relevant stakeholders can request and use the data for research. Who can apply the data is:

- Any natural or legal person
- Exclusion based on the use and compliance with safeguards
- Ineligibility is conditional not categorical- if the applicant meet legal and technical safeguards

The application process is as follows:

1. Submit a request (purpose of data, description, data protection and security measures, ethical approvals) to the Health Data access body (HDAB) in the relevant member state
2. Evaluation by HDAB (purpose as permitted secondary use, and appropriate safeguards, and if the data requested is proportionate to the purpose)
3. Issuance of data permit (scope and duration of access conditions for data use, obligations for reporting and transparency)

HDABs can charge fees that cover the costs of their operations, for some health data users higher fees can result.

Conditions to be met to get granted access include the following:

- Permitted purpose
- Necessity and proportionality
- GDPR legal basis- in case of pseudonymised data
- Security safeguards – secure processing environments
- Transparency- obligation for publishing the data (18 Months)

A few examples of the ethical dimension which must be considered in regard to data and AI in healthcare are

- Clear purpose justification
- Detailed risk assessment
- Relevant mitigation measures
- Ethics committee approval
- Policy for incidental findings

2.5.2. Intellectual Property in AI

Petra Zarska (Intellectual Property Manager, AMIRES) talked about AI in regards to intellectual property and how developed models can be protected for further exploitation.

AI is transforming the healthcare industry through diverse type of applications. An analysis of over 10K healthcare-related AI patents was performed, with 66.9 % coming from China Intellectual property administration, 25.5 % from the United States Patent and Trademark Office, 4.74% from Korean Intellectual Property Office, 1.7% come from European Patent Office and 1.5% from Japan Patent Office. The top countries where patents were filed are China, US, South Korea, Germany and Japan. Siemens Healthcare GmbH is the second organisation with most patent applications after the Ping An Technology Co Ltd.

IP generated for AI to be used for healthcare applications can be protected through trade secrets (decisional algorithm), patents or copyright (data set used to power the algorithm).

Any good IP strategy should be based on the overall business strategy. For example, an algorithm that processes CT (computed tomography) images to diagnose a variety of medical conditions. The process could be licensed as trade secret, but all parties must maintain secrecy, making broad licencing challenging. In comparison, patent licensing delivers the ability to publicly disclose and license broadly.

However, claims directed solely to AI algorithms or data processing without a technical application are not patentable. Therefore, it must be avoided framing the invention as a mere mathematical method or abstract idea. This means that the claim must show how the AI is applied in a technical context, for example controlling a medical device or processing physiological signals in a novel way (improving accuracy if a hearth monitoring device or reducing false positives of cancer, etc).

According to the European Patent Office (EPO): [Guidelines for Examination in the European Patent Office](#) April 2025 edition,

- Whether two text documents in respect of their textual content belong to the same “class” of documents is not a technical issue.
- A comparison with what a human being would do is not a suitable basis for distinguishing between technical and non-technical steps.
- The mere fact that an algorithm leads to reproducible results does not imply that it makes a technical contribution.

Key takeaways from the presentation were outlined as follows:

- Consider the international patent trends in the field
- Establish and execute a clear IP strategy in line with business strategy
- Identify the technical character of AI healthcare technology before patenting

2.5.3. Designing Medical AI with Her in Mind: Personalization, Transparency, and the Power of Perspective

Sepinoud Azimi (Assistant Professor, Delft University of Technology) provided insights into the broad topic of gendered innovation and how to create a more inclusive research landscape.

A way to picture the presentation regarding the gender dimension of the medical research was through the Aesop Fable: The fox and stork, in which both animals served dinner to the other on a way that the other cannot eat it due to their anatomy. This is the case when physiological differences between men and women are not considered¹⁴:

- Women are 50% more likely to misdiagnosed after heart attack, since women usually show different symptoms.
- Usually, women are given less pain medication in emergency rooms since their pain is underestimated.
- Crash test dummies are based on average male bodies
- HealthKit apple app did not include a menstrual tracker at launch
- Women are frequently excluded from clinical trials due to the hormonal fluctuations.

Biased health data is a mirror of the society, and gender bias is found in many cases, for example in AI tools screening for liver disease, in large language models such as ChatGPT, and many others. The issue on the bias is due to the problem framing, data collection, model training, hyperparameter tuning and evaluation of the models.

Dr. Azimi underlines that a general design shift is needed to ensure better representation of women, towards Personalization, Transparency (black box) and Perspective (diverse teams).

Design teams should always be inclusive because will help generate the right questions to be considered during the development process. It is important that the tools are built with and not only for women, therefore she suggests the following action points:

- Developers: involve women in each level
- Researchers: demand sex-disaggregated results and audit datasets
- Funders: support inclusive design
- Policymakers: require gender impact assessments for medical AI.

Returning to the fable at the end of the presentation, it is underlined that it is not just about serving better meals, but making sure everyone gets a seat at the table when the menu is written.

2.5.4. Stakeholder involvement in the development of AI for Healthcare

John Kellas (DPhil candidate, University of Oxford & Innovation and Community Engagement Consultant, ThisEquals company) is leading the activities of stakeholder engagement in the [NetZeroAICT project](#).

¹⁴ Criado Perez, C. *Invisible Women: Exposing Data Bias in a World Designed for Men*

Stakeholders of health AI include patients, members of the public and professionals. In UK health research, “Public Involvement” is a shorthand way of referring to patient and public involvement and engagement. The UK National Institute for Health Research (NIHR) provides useful frameworks for co-operation with patient and public stakeholders in research initiatives:

- Involvement- with, by, or in partnership with members of the public rather than to, about or for them
- Engagement - where information and knowledge about research is provided and disseminated
- Participation- where people take part in a research study.

The UK NIHR standards for public involvement describe the importance of working together, communications, inclusive opportunities, impact, governance, support and learning. The mechanisms of involvement include : co-investigation, co design, co-production and co-management. Public involvement can support research and product scoping and agenda setting, co-design and development, validation and feedback, and monitoring and iteration development through deployment.

It is important to involve members of the public in research because people who are affected by research have the right to have a say in it, because they provide a different perspective, they can help in tailor the research to the needs of specific communities, make the research more relevant and keep projects grounded in valuing the public good over private in interest. In addition, many funding bodies and ethics committees will ask about plans of public involvement.

The NetZeroAICT project has implemented patient, public and professional involvement as core to the trustworthiness approach to research and product development through establishing a patient and public advisory group (PAG) and facilitating representation from this group in leadership meetings. The PAG is formed of 14 members, who were recruited via patient networks and advocacy groups, and are diverse in terms of nationality, ethnicity, gender, occupation, educational level and knowledge of AI. The PAG members are considered as critical friends invited to provide input across all workstreams–. Critical friends ask challenging questions, offer constructive criticism, express opinions and want to help and support.

According to the European Commission’s “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI” developed by the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI HLEG), building a trustworthy artificial intelligence solution is based on robustness, lawfulness and ethics, and it requires the following pillars:

1. human agency and oversight
2. technical robustness and safety
3. privacy and data governance
4. transparency
5. diversity, non-discrimination and fairness
6. societal and environmental wellbeing
7. accountability

However, we might consider an 8th pillar, or a dynamic that brings the 7 pillar Trustworthy AI model to life: democratic deliberation, through which public involvement can support quality assurance and quality control.

2.5.5. Topics of discussion during Q&A session

The following topics were raised for discussion during Q&A of “Enabling AI applications” session:”

- **Governance, Ethics & Policy in the European Health Data Space (EHDS)**
 - Expertise of Health Access Data Bodies: Understanding their function in data governance and access control.
 - EHDS implementation timeline: Key milestones and expected rollout phases.

- How EHDS ensures ethical and legal compliance: Balancing cross-border data sharing, innovation, and patient rights in AI-driven healthcare.
- **Transparency, IP & Ethical AI**
 - Balancing transparency and intellectual property: Navigating the tension between explainable AI and proprietary algorithms in clinical settings.
 - Ethical implications of AI in patient care: Ensuring responsible innovation without compromising patient trust.
- **Inclusion, Diversity & Public Engagement**
 - Inclusion of diverse perspectives in AI design: How involving women and underrepresented groups helps reduce bias and improve outcomes.
 - Engaging public and patient groups effectively: Best practices for meaningful involvement.
 - Selection and engagement of public advisory members: Tailoring involvement strategies based on member profiles (e.g., professionals vs. interested citizens).

2.6. Summary /conclusions/take aways

- AI use in healthcare and life sciences is increasing at accelerated pace and we need to adapt, learn and use it
- In military operations, tools like AI are essential in constrained environments to support rapid decision-making and efficient use of limited resources
- AI in life sciences is being used for drug discovery, support prediction in treatment routes, cell tracking, and many other applications, this has been propelled by the Nobel Prize in 2024 for the AlphaFold model
- The specialty of Medicine in which AI has been used the most is in Radiology and medical imaging
- AI demonstrates to be effective in predicting risk for several diseases through the analysis of dental imaging
- AI is a promising tool to assist stroke care and support cardiology risk assessment
- Data is required to train algorithms, and this can be facilitated by the European Health Data Space for Research.
- Intellectual property of AI solutions in healthcare and life sciences must align with the core business model and in order to be protected by a patent should cover a technical application
- AI design must be inclusive, transparent in order to be personalized
- Public engagement as part of a proper stakeholder strategy should be considered along any AI research project life cycle.
- AI solutions in healthcare and life sciences should be built with the affected people, not for. Inclusivity supports equitability.

3. Annex 1: Agenda

AI IN HEALTHCARE & LIFESCIENCES

From excellent science to patient benefit

9:00	Registration & Welcome Coffee
10:00	Introduction to the AI in Healthcare & Lifesciences event Cecilia Sahlgrén, Åbo Akademi University / Martina Nešverová, Amires
10:15	Keynote presentation: AI applications in the military Martin Majovsky, Military University Hospital Prague
11:00	AI in Lifesciences Moderator: Mariana Pacheco Blanco, AMIRES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≡ NAP4DIVE project: Utilizing AI as non-animal tools to assess nanoparticle-mediated drug delivery over the BBB Cecilia Sahlgrén, Åbo Akademi University ≡ Tumor-LN-oC project: Real-Time Cell Tracking in Tumor-LN-oC Deploying ML models at the edge Vassilis Sarantos, Director & CEO, RayFos Ltd. ≡ OASIS project: Bridging Data and Decision-Making in ADC Treatment with AI Noémie Corcos, Translational Project Manager, Institute Gustave Roussy ≡ Personalized Medicine through AI: Integrating Multi-modal Data for Revolutionizing Healthcare Carine Poussin, Head of AI for Life Sciences, CSEM ≡ Q&A Session
12:00	Group Photo & Networking Lunch
13:00	AI-enabled care Moderator: Panagiotis Chatzis, AMIRES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≡ The present and future of AI in Radiology Erik Ranschaert, Diagnostic Radiologist, Senior Medical Advisor, Visiting Professor, Ghent University ≡ AI to assist stroke care and life after stroke - learnings from RES-Q+ Terry Quinn, Professor, University of Glasgow ≡ Trustworthy AI in cardiology: AI4HF and DT4H insights Cristian Izquierdo Morcillo, Scientific Lead, University of Barcelona ≡ AI in Dental Care Max Heiland, Director & Chairman Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin ≡ Q&A Session
14:30	Coffee Break
15:00	Enabling AI Applications Moderator: Kristin Aldag, AMIRES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≡ Legal Implications of the European Health Data Space for Research Michal Koščík, Head of Department of Public Health & Vice Dean, Masaryk University Brno ≡ Intellectual Property in AI Petra Žárská, Intellectual Property Manager, Amires ≡ Designing Medical AI with Her in Mind: Personalization, Transparency, and the Power of Perspective Sepinoud Azimi, Assistant Professor, Delft University of Technology ≡ Stakeholder involvement in the development of AI for Healthcare John Kellas, Innovation & Community Engagement Consultant, PhD Candidate, University of Oxford ≡ Q&A Session
16:00	Networking Reception

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